

TECHNICAL, ECONOMIC AND ECOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE USE OF NATURAL RESOURCES IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE**Nasirova Afruz Sattar,***Odlar Yurdu University, K. Rahimov. 13, AZ1072, Baku, Azerbaijan***ORCID:** 0000-0001-7910-4440**Shikhiyev Ziyad Zaur***Odlar Yurdu University, K. Rahimov. 13, AZ1072, Baku, Azerbaijan***ORCID:** 0009-0004-3674-9520**Abstract**

Climate change has further increased the relevance of economic and environmental problems related to the use of natural resources. In this study, a technical, economic and environmental analysis of the use of natural resources was conducted, direct and indirect assessment methods, environmental audit and long-term forecasting approaches were applied. The results show that, the combined application of economic mechanisms with environmental incentives promotes the economical use of resources, reduces waste and strengthens environmental safety. The development of eco-entrepreneurship and eco-management improves both economic indicators and social well-being in the production and service sectors. The study proves that efficient management of natural resources is not only a measure of environmental protection, but also a key condition for sustainable economic development.

Keywords: Climate change, Natural resources, Ecological economics, Sustainable development, Eco-management, Azerbaijan

INTRODUCTION

Climate change has further increased the relevance of economic and ecological problems related to the use of natural resources in modern times. Although the interaction between the development of society and nature is based on balance, anthropogenic impacts disrupt this balance and complicate the efficient use of resources. In this regard, the study of the economic and ecological foundations of nature use is of great scientific and practical importance for ensuring sustainable development.

The modern concept of nature use is not limited only to the extraction and consumption of resources, but is also closely related to their protection, restoration and protection of the interests of future generations. Efficient use, in addition to ensuring economic growth, serves to reduce environmental risks, protect environmental quality and improve social well-being. On the contrary, inefficient use leads to the emergence of ecological crises, increased economic losses and degradation of natural systems (*Goychayli & Ismayilov, 2006*).

The scientific foundations of this field are built on the integration of economics and ecology. The economic approach is concerned with the assessment of resources, the costs and benefits of their use, and the ecological approach is concerned with reducing environmental impacts and protecting natural systems. Thus, the technical, economic and ecological analysis of nature use is complex and requires the application of various methodological approaches.

Historically, starting from classical economic schools, the economic aspects of the relationship between nature and society have been discussed, and since the middle of the 20th century, as a result of the aggravation of environmental problems, “environmental economics” has been formed as a separate scientific field (*Ricardo, D., 1817; Malthus, T.R., 1798; Marx, K., 1867*). In modern times, the economics of nature use

is closely integrated with ecological economics, dealing with resource assessment, the formation of environmental policy, and the development of sustainable development models.

In countries like Azerbaijan, which are rich in natural resources but are vulnerable to the effects of climate change, studying these issues is of particular importance. The aim of the article is to examine the economic and ecological foundations of the use of natural resources against the backdrop of climate change, identify existing problems and provide scientifically based recommendations for their solution.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Financing of environmental measures and formation of funds have been carried out with different approaches in the experience of different countries. During the USSR, the amount of financial resources allocated for nature protection measures constituted a very small percentage of national income (0.8–1.2% for the whole Union, and 0.3–0.5% in some republics). In modern times, this trend has continued, and budget resources allocated for environmental purposes have been less than 1% of GDP. However, the amount of economic damage resulting from environmental degradation in some countries constitutes 8–15% of GDP, which indicates the inadequacy of financial mechanisms (*Goychayli, Mikayilov, & Abdullayev, 1996*).

In the experience of the Russian Federation, the formation of ecological funds was carried out by dividing them between federal, regional and local budgets, but serious violations were observed in the use of allocated funds. Similar problems existed in Azerbaijan, the rules of ecological funds stipulated in the legislation were not followed, the allocated funds were included in the state budget and redirected to other areas. This situation led to the lack of sustainability in the financing

of ecological programs (*Ministry of Ecology of the Russian Federation, 2019; Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2020*).

Financial support from international organizations and donor countries has played an important role in the implementation of environmental measures. National action plans prepared with the assistance of the World Bank and other international funds have been financed through a tender mechanism, but transparency problems have been observed in the use of these resources (*World Bank, 2005; OECD, 2017*).

Environmental insurance and leasing have also been considered as alternative financing mechanisms. Although environmental insurance creates a legal framework for compensating for risks arising from the activities of enterprises, it is accompanied by an additional financial burden. Leasing, on the other hand, is considered a flexible mechanism for long-term financing of environmental protection equipment, but is limited by a high-risk factor.

Overall, the existing literature shows that the effectiveness of environmental funds and alternative financing mechanisms is still limited. The amount of funds allocated is insufficient compared to the scale of environmental problems and is often symbolic in nature. This confirms the existence of institutional gaps in the financing of environmental policy.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

In this study, direct, indirect and modern methods were applied for the economic valuation of natural resources. Direct methods evaluated the rent indicators and production costs formed as a result of the use of resources based on the rent approach, the cost method and the cost-resource approach. Indirect methods were applied in cases where market prices were not available based on the alternative value concept, general economic assessment, subjective approach, transportation costs and real estate prices. Modern approaches included the re-production method and the monopoly-management approach based on payments determined by management bodies to restore the ecological balance (*Daly, H.E., & Farley, J., 2011; Pearce, D., & Turner, R.K., 1990*).

A complex methodological framework has been established for the analysis of ecological and economic processes. At the first stage, a system of ecological and economic indicators and standards was developed based on balance methods, comparative factors and statistical reporting forms. At the next stage, the goals and objectives of ecological and economic analysis were determined, and EIA (Environmental Impact Assessment) and ecological expertise procedures were applied to assess the ecological safety and socio-economic results of projects (*Bayramov, 2011; Jafarova, 2014*).

In addition, an ecological audit was conducted, the stages of selection of objects, collection of initial data, analytical assessment and final reporting were carried out sequentially. Finally, long-term forecasting, balance approaches, extrapolation, expert assessment and modeling methods were used to predict and plan the use

of nature. This process was completed by the preparation of ecological passports and the formation of regional programs.

RESULTS

The results of the study showed that, the economic mechanisms of natural resource use and environmental incentives are multifaceted. The analysis proves that, the parallel application of positive and negative economic incentives serves to protect environmental interests in entrepreneurial activity and increase economic efficiency. The introduction of resource and emission payments promotes the economical use of resources, reduces waste and creates a financial source for environmental protection measures.

Analysis of the volume and application mechanisms of pollution charges shows that their real incentive effect is weakened due to insufficient indexation and inflation adjustment. Despite the increase in charges in Azerbaijan and other CIS countries, the weakness of monitoring and accountability mechanisms prevents the full achievement of environmental results. International experience shows that, charges should not only serve the function of collecting funds, but also of stimulating technological modernization.

The results also prove that, the application of eco-entrepreneurship and eco-management creates both economic and social positive effects in the production, service and financial sectors. The development of eco-business ensures the efficient use of resources through waste disposal, reuse of raw materials and energy saving. This not only improves the economic performance of enterprises, but also contributes to environmental protection.

The effectiveness of eco-entrepreneurship manifests itself at different levels:

- At the societal level – reduction of pollution and increase of social welfare;
- At the production level – expansion of use of recycled raw materials and reduction of production costs;
- At the firm level – strengthening of ecological image, achievement of competitive advantage in the market and formation of additional income.

The application of eco-management, along with planning, monitoring and control of environmental safety measures in enterprises, creates conditions for the provision of products and services that meet the requirements of consumers through ecological marketing. This approach increases long-term sustainability and leads to an increase in the ecological and economic effect.

In general, the conducted analyses prove that, the management of nature use is not only an environmental protection measure, but also an important mechanism for increasing economic efficiency.

Analyses of natural resource management show that, efficient use and conservation of resources are key to ecological and economic sustainability. The results show that, conservation and proper management of natural resources not only ensure ecological stability, but also create new opportunities for economic development. According to the observations:

- Resource utilization – efficient use of recycled raw materials and waste reduction reduces production costs and increases productivity.
- Energy savings – economical use of energy resources has a positive impact on the economic performance of enterprises, while also reducing environmental risks.
- Environmental safety – as a result of management measures, environmental pollution is minimized, which leads to an increase in public welfare.
- Socio-economic impacts – as a result of nature use management, the environmental image is strengthened, consumer confidence increases, and a competitive advantage is formed in the market.

Overall, the results show that, nature use management is not only an environmental protection measure, but also an important mechanism for increasing economic efficiency. This approach plays a key role in the implementation of a sustainable development strategy and produces positive results at both the production and societal levels.

CONCLUSION

The results of the study show that, economic mechanisms for the use of natural resources should be aimed not only at financial accumulation, but also at ensuring environmental safety. Proper standardization, indexation and targeting of payments to environmental goals stimulate the efficient use of resources and serve to reduce environmental risks.

In Azerbaijan, it is important to strengthen the legal and regulatory framework in this area, expand the monitoring system and apply international experience. The development of ecological entrepreneurship and eco-management, in addition to improving the economic performance of enterprises, strengthens environmental protection and contributes to the well-being of society.

Thus, efficient management of natural resources acts as one of the main indicators of a sustainable development strategy and plays an important role in ensuring both economic and environmental sustainability.

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